

DESTINATION EARTH CO-DESIGN TOOLKIT

Worksheet 3

Guiding principles to build co-design workshops

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document focuses on Phase #3 of the co-design process, which corresponds to the organization and implementation of co-design workshops. It provides guiding principles for structuring, facilitating, and documenting these workshops in a way that ensures continuity with the previous diagnostic work and alignment with the strategic objectives of Destination Earth (DestinE).

Building on the insights gathered during Phase #1 (Approaching Users) and Phase #2 (Co-design Diagnosis), this phase represents the operational core of the co-design journey. It transforms analytical understanding into collaborative action, where service providers, users, and platform representatives jointly shape and refine service concepts, prototypes, and integration strategies.

The document outlines both the technical and relational challenges that workshops should address, emphasizing the need to structure sessions according to the specific issues identified during the diagnosis. It highlights the importance of progressively tackling these challenges through a series of workshops, rather than attempting to address all issues in a single session.

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1. Introduction to the Workshop Phase

1.1. Introduction to the Phase #3 – Co-Design Workshops

The third phase of the co-design methodology consists in the implementation of co-design actions, through the organization of co-design workshops. The goal of these workshops is to unlock the different blocking points faced by the service. They can be focused on clarifying the users' needs, but also on a variety of other purpose such as framing a working relationship with potential partners, fixing integration issues with infrastructure providers, or envisioning new uses for an existing service for instance.

The co-design workshops represent the most interactive phase of the DestinE co-design process. These workshops serve as a collaborative space where service providers and users come together to design both DestinE services and the “co”, meaning, the techniques, tools and methods involved in shaping collective action. Given this diversity of purpose and action regime that could be required during this phase, two points are critical when organizing co-design actions in this phase:

- 1) **The co-design workshops should be structured as to move forward gradually in resolving the problems identified in the diagnosis:** not all problems will be solved at the same time in a single workshop. Therefore, problems identified during the diagnosis phase should serve as a guide to structure the sequence of co-design workshops. The Worksheet 3.1 gives some guidelines to structure the sequence of co-design workshops.
- 2) Since each of the workshop should be focused on a specific problem identified during the diagnosis, **the protocols followed during these workshops should be adapted to these specific problems.** Typically, this action phase can be built on as many different protocols as there are workshops. However, this worksheet gives some guidelines to structure these protocols.

1.2. Position of this document within the co-design workflow

The co-design workshops should be structured based on the insights gathered from the previous phases, namely **Phase #1 “Approaching Users”** and **Phase #2 “Co-design Diagnosis”** (notably through the Data-Information-Value Framework). The diagnosis phase provides the basis for identifying the challenges to be addressed through the workshops and for determining how the sequence of sessions should be organized. Each workshop serves as both a continuation and a new iteration of the process, refining earlier insights while generating new ones that may reshape the following steps.

The co-design process functions as a dynamic cycle of exploration, discussion, and adjustment. The workshops engage users directly to identify and clarify needs, co-design potential solutions, explore their scalability, and build shared understanding around objectives, integration, and feasibility. Feedback and discoveries from one session inform the design of the next, allowing the process to remain adaptive to evolving knowledge, contexts, and relationships.

A variety of outcomes can emerge from this iterative work. These results form the inputs to Phase #4, “Outcomes Diagram,” which consolidates and formalizes the insights and commitments reached during the workshops. Based on the relationships initiated and refined throughout this process, the final phase aims to establish a clear and actionable plan with the actors involved, ensuring that progress achieved through co-design translates into concrete, sustained developments.

1.3. Objectives

The co-design workshops are the operational core of the co-design process. They translate analytical insights from the diagnosis into collaborative actions that shape concrete service developments and integration. Each session is an opportunity to design both the relationship between stakeholders and the technical components while clarifying uncertainties, and progressively aligning user expectations with the technical and organizational capacities of the service developer and DestinE. The primary objectives of the co-design workshops are to:

- **Define and refine user requirements:** Build upon and further clarify the needs identified during the diagnosis phase, ensuring a precise and comprehensive understanding of user expectations. This process establishes a solid foundation that aligns service objectives with actual user demands.
- **Co-design and iterate service prototypes:** Engage users in a co-design process to define, develop, and enhance service functionalities. The workshops allow for testing and exploration of potential use cases and implementation strategies, gathering iterative feedback to ensure the service remains relevant and user centered.
- **Establish sustainable cooperation modalities:** Formalize interaction frameworks, define roles, responsibilities, and feedback loops between service providers and users. This structured approach fosters trust and supports a continuous, collaborative relationship throughout the service lifecycle.
- **Identify pathways for future development:** Actively explore unknowns, emerging needs, and potential new stakeholders to engage, ensuring the co-design process remains adaptive and resilient. This proactive stance supports an evolving service that grows in alignment with user ecosystems and technological advancements.

1.4. Context of use

The challenges and guidelines presented in this worksheet are applicable to a wide range of co-design settings related to the development and refinement of DestinE services. They are intended to provide a flexible yet structured framework that can be adapted to different contexts, levels of maturity, and stakeholder configurations. Whether the service developer is initiating a new co-design process from scratch or advancing an existing service toward operational integration, the principles described can guide the structuring of workshops, the facilitation of interactions, and the translation of insights into operationalizable outcomes.

Future versions of this worksheet will further detail specific co-design protocols, tailored to various contexts. These extensions will include methodological variations to address the particularities of each application domain.

2. Structuring a consistent series of workshops

2.1. From co-design diagnosis towards co-design workshops

A successful co-design process relies on the insights gained from the co-design Diagnosis (Phase #2). The diagnosis provides a comprehensive understanding of the usage ecosystems, highlighting the needs, operational contexts, and interdependencies of potential users. By analyzing these findings, service providers can design workshops that are not only relevant but also highly effective in addressing the specific challenges and goals of the stakeholders involved.

The co-design diagnosis allows service providers to clearly define the **scope of each workshop, identify key participants, and tailor activities to specific user needs.** Indeed, each workshop should be focused on addressing one (or a few) specific challenges identified during the diagnosis phase. This ensures that the workshops are strategically focused, with each phase designed to build upon the last.

Without this rigorous analytical groundwork, workshops risk being misaligned or too broad in their objectives, leading to suboptimal outcomes and diminished stakeholder engagement. The results of the diagnosis, therefore, serve as a dynamic roadmap, continuously refined to adapt to new insights as the co-design process evolves.

Various kind of challenges can be identified during the diagnosis, either related to **technical matters** or to **relational matters**. Both kind of challenges have to be adressed through specific co-design actions during the workshop phase.

2.1.1. Key challenges to be adressed from a technical perspective

The co-design process should always be structured around three central components: Usefulness, Operability, and Usability. Together, they form the pillars of service co-design, ensuring that each dimension of value creation, from user needs to operational implementation and end-user adoption, is addressed in a systematic and complementary manner. These three components and the associated challenges should be addressed by the service provider through specific types of co-design workshops sessions.

Moreover, two transversal aspects, Scalability and Sustainability, are also central to the successful development of any service, and should be considered all along the co-design journey. They ensure that each design choice contributes to long-term robustness, adaptability, and integration within the broader DestinE ecosystem.

The table 1 gives a synthetic overview on how different types of workshops can be organized to address each of these components for service success and adoption. More detailed guidelines on how to structure consistent co-design workshop sessions depending on the challenges to address are provided in the *worksheets 3.1 (Usefulness), 3.2 (Operability) and 3.3 (Usability).*

Components of the co-design process	
Components	Purpose of the workshops sessions
Usefulness	<p>The Usefulness workshop sessions focus on identifying and refining the needs of potential users and translating them into coherent service requirements. They explore what problems the service aims to solve, what value it brings, and how DestinE data and computing capacities can contribute to addressing those needs.</p> <p>Usefulness workshops help move from abstract ideas to a structured understanding of user contexts and priorities, forming the conceptual foundation for service design.</p> <p><i>(see Worksheet 3.1 – Usefulness Workshops).</i></p>
Operability	<p>The Operability workshop sessions translate user needs into technically and organizationally feasible solutions. It examines how the service can be implemented within the available infrastructure, how it interacts with DestinE resources, and what governance or partnership arrangements are required.</p> <p>Operability workshops help service providers and potential partners to align technical constraints, data availability, and resource capacities to produce viable prototypes and implementation plans.</p> <p><i>(see Worksheet 3.2 – Operability Workshops).</i></p>
Usability	<p>The Usability workshop sessions test whether the designed services are accessible, understandable, and easily integrated into users' existing workflows, tools and practices. It focuses on user experience, feedback, and adoption barriers, ensuring that services developed through co-design are not only operational but also effectively used and valued by their target communities.</p> <p>Usability workshops therefore close the loop between technical design and practical application.</p> <p><i>(see Worksheet 3.3 – Usability Workshops).</i></p>
Sustainability	<p>Ensuring the sustainability of the service must be a concern that guides all co-design actions during the journey. This means that the major issues related to sustainability should be considered throughout all workshops as a common thread in the co-design efforts. For example, during workshops with users, their willingness to pay can be explored, as well as the constraints and processes to consider for a commercial relationship during workshops dedicated to usefulness or usability. Similarly, beyond technical issues, those related to intellectual property and costs can be addressed with partners during workshops focused on operability, for instance.</p> <p><i>(for a comprehensive template to address service sustainability see Worksheet 4.1 – Sustainability Canvas)</i></p>
Scalability	<p>Scalability ensures that services developed for a specific use case can be extended or adapted to other contexts, users, or applications within DestinE and beyond. A such, the design of scalable services implies to consider specific actions related to usefulness, operability and usability workshops. Typically, the more diverse are the profiles of potential users involved in workshops focused on sustainability, the more the service provider is likely to identify scalable generic features. Also, the technical scalability of the service should be considered as a critical point for discussion during workshops focused on operability with potential partners.</p>

Depending on the specific needs identified during the diagnosis phase the actual number and configuration of these different types of workshop can vary. Typically, the structure of the co-design journey may vary depending on whether the service provider already has an operational

service to improve or is starting from an early-stage concept. Service providers operating mature services may combine or shorten phases, focusing on specific refinements, whereas early-stage projects may require several workshops within each phase to progressively build shared understanding and technical feasibility.

As a reference structure, the three-phase co-design journey articulating Usefulness (1), Operability (2) and Usability (3) remains the most effective and balanced configuration. It provides a clear path from understanding needs (Usefulness), to making the service feasible (Operability), to ensuring its adoption (Usability), while maintaining a long-term perspective through Sustainability and Scalability.

2.1.2. Key challenges to be addressed from a relational perspective

Beyond technical challenges related to service development, co-design workshops should be structured to address the relational challenges related to establishing consistent working relationships with users.

Connecting DestinE data to potential usages can be challenging since it involves bridging people who usually evolve in highly different spheres, who have very little in common, and who might not be even aware of the existence of one another. In other words, the actors are separated by a form of “**grand distance**”¹, making them appear as largely unknown to each other. In such conditions, collective action seems nowhere near guaranteed, if even possible.

Given this situation, three key relational objectives should be kept in mind when organizing a co-design workshop:

- 1) **Workshops should serve the design of the ‘co-‘:** An effective co-design approach implies to clearly acknowledge that the co-design workshops should not only focus on the design of the service, but also on the design of the relationships, i.e. ‘co-design’ has to design the ‘co’. It means that the workshops should support a clear formulation of how the stakeholders involved would work together. Typically, the protocols of the workshops should integrate this aspect by always organizing a final phase dedicated to building working plans and/or agreements for future cooperation between participants. Also, all along the workshops, the participants should strain to navigate simultaneously the ‘what’ and ‘how (together)’: each time a technical need or feature is discussed, some ways to collectively work on it should be discussed also.
- 2) **Building a resilient fit instead of a ‘quick fit’:** The co-design actions workshops should be conducted with the objective to establish a ‘resilient fit’ between participants, rather than a ‘quick fit’. ‘Quick-fit’ actions would focus on finding one type of interaction between data and usages ecosystems (single list of requirements with one user, in a punctual relationship). Whereas ‘resilient-fit’ actions aim at generating a range of alternatives (regarding the lists of requirements, the stakeholders involved, the types of partnerships), allowing a better adaptation to future surprises or unexpected constraints. This point appears to be crucial in order to foster the use of DestinE in a long-term perspective, as service providers will have to deal with constant evolutions of both sensors, data and models and the different usage fields. In this perspective, each workshop should be designed to progressively shape and consolidate ‘building blocks’ of the long-term development of the service’s strategy, intertwined with the evolution of both DestinE and usage fields.

¹ Grand Distance refers to a situation where service providers and their potential users shows a high degree of distance on many dimensions : cognitive, social, organizational, institutional and geographical

- 3) Building a Collective Design Capability:** Throughout the workshops, a continuous effort to foster collective learning among users, service providers, and platform representatives should be favorized. Each participant should bring insights and expertise, and the co-design workshops should create a space for these perspectives to converge. This shared understanding enhances the quality of the services developed and builds stronger relationships among stakeholders. As such, the co-design workshops stand as a place for collective mutual learning instead of session merely oriented at unidirectional data collection regarding user needs. By the end of the process, all participants should have a deeper understanding of each other's competencies, goals, and challenges, which is essential for sustaining collaboration beyond the co-design workshops and unique service development. In other words, this collective and mutual learning should support the emergence of a collective design capability that would, in the end, foster and ease the emergence of subsequent opportunities for collaboration

Figure 2. Key Challenges of the co-design process and workshop sessions

2.2. The key components of a successful co-design workshop

Facing the above-mentioned challenges (both on the technical and relational aspect) requires a thorough preparation for the co-design sessions. In particular, three critical components stand at the heart of co-design sessions and should be well prepared before the sessions:

- 1) **An agenda** should be carefully prepared as to build a constructive dialogue and to ensure that the workshop’s specific objectives will be achieved.
- 2) **Close interactions** should be organized to guide users in the expression of their needs.
- 3) **Templates** should be carefully prepared to provide a clear, common and unambiguous support for dialogue and interaction.

Figure 3. The key components of co-design Workshops

2.2.1. Agenda design: Gradually build a constructive dialogue

The success of any co-design workshop heavily depends on the thoughtful preparation of its agenda. The agenda serves as the structural backbone of the session, shaping the flow of interactions and ensuring that each participant’s contributions are valued. A well-designed agenda is not merely a schedule but a tool to foster meaningful dialogue and collaboration, balancing structured presentations with open, flexible discussions. An agenda should be shared in advance with participants to allow preparation.

Here are some key principles to build an effective agenda for co-design workshops:

- A first critical principle is providing **contextual grounding**. The agenda should include a segment where the project’s goals, scope, and the service developer’s position within the broader initiative are clearly explained. This ensures that all participants share a common understanding of the project’s framework and objectives, helping to align expectations and focus discussions. Also, as the overall co-design process moves forward, it is important to systematically recall the previous steps, and the progress made at the beginning of every workshop.
- To enhance user engagement, it is essential to incorporate **visual and interactive elements**, such as the presentation of prototypes or examples of DestinE’s capabilities. These tangible demonstrations make complex concepts more accessible, particularly for non-expert users, and help stimulate their imagination, making it easier for them to express their needs and envision potential solutions.

- Another key principle in agenda design is creating space for **active listening and user expression**. During co-design, understanding user perspectives is paramount. Therefore, the agenda should allocate ample time for users to articulate their needs, concerns, and ideas. This open dialogue not only enriches the co-design process but also fosters a sense of ownership and trust among participants.
- Finally, the agenda should reserve time to **define next steps**. This closing segment is crucial for maintaining momentum and ensuring continuity in the co-design process. It provides an opportunity to agree on upcoming meetings, set deadlines, and outline the tasks required before the next session. By doing so, the relationship between the service developer and the users is reinforced, and participants remain actively engaged.

Following these core principles, a generic structure for the agenda of co-design workshops could be the following (instance for a 90' workshop):

- 1) Roundtable (5')
- 2) Introduction to the workshop (10')
 - Recall of the objectives of the overall process
 - Recall of the previous co-design actions and the state of the process
 - Introduction to the objectives of this workshop
 - Introduction to the protocol used in the workshop
- 3) Demonstration of prototypes, and/or existing services that could be consistent (15')
- 4) Working session based on template and specific exercises prepared by the service developer (45')
- 5) Next steps, and working plan (15')

2.2.2. Interactions facilitation through co-design

Effective facilitation is a cornerstone of successful co-design workshops. The facilitator's role goes far beyond timekeeping or coordination as it is about *creating the conditions for collaboration*, i.e. a setting where participants feel confident to share, challenge, and build upon one another's ideas. Facilitators act as catalysts of dialogue, guiding participants through uncertainty while allowing space for creativity, diversity of thought, and collective discovery to emerge.

A first critical task for facilitators is to **establish a clear and inclusive structure for interaction**. This begins with defining the participation dynamics and group configurations. When stakeholders come from different backgrounds or domains, mixed or parallel group formats can be strategically chosen. For instance, **small heterogeneous sub-groups** can stimulate cross-fertilization between perspectives, while **homogeneous groups** (e.g., technical vs. policy users) allow deeper dives into specialized issues. Alternating between the two formats during the workshop ensures both diversity and focus.

A second task is to **ensure inclusivity and balanced participation**. Creating a psychologically safe environment is key to making all voices heard. Facilitators can:

- Begin with a short "warm-up" or introductory round to humanize the group and lower participation barriers.
- Use **structured turn-taking** during early discussions to ensure that everyone speaks at least once.
- Introduce **visual or written tools** (sticky notes, digital boards, feedback cards) that allow quieter participants to contribute non-verbally.
- Reformulate or summarize contributions neutrally to validate input and encourage further elaboration.
- Politely manage dominant voices by redirecting ("Let's hear from someone who hasn't spoken yet") or parking off-topic ideas for later review.

Third, facilitators should focus on **turning conversation into actionable insight**. Co-design workshops generate abundant ideas, but without synthesis, this richness can be lost. To maintain focus and progression, facilitators should:

- Regularly summarize emerging points and check for group consensus (“Can we agree that these are the three main issues?”).
- Use **visual mapping tools** such as collective canvases or clustering boards to group ideas thematically.
- Translate open discussions into **clear outputs**, such as prioritized user needs, refined service features, or next-step actions.
- End each block or exercise with a “checkpoint” moment where the group confirms what has been learned or decided before moving forward.

Finally, effective facilitation requires **adaptability and reflective pacing**. While workshops benefit from a predefined agenda, discussions can uncover unexpected but valuable insights. Facilitators should remain attentive to signals (energy levels, emerging tensions, or new opportunities) and adjust timing or activities when necessary. For instance, if a key topic generates strong engagement, extending that session may be more beneficial than strictly adhering to the schedule. The goal is not rigid control, but to sustain a productive flow of exploration that keeps participants aligned with the workshop’s objectives while valuing their collective intelligence.

2.2.1. Co-design templates: support the ideation and capture insights

Figure 4. Examples of templates available in the co-design toolkit

The modular logic of co-design templates

Co-design templates are an important component of the workshop phase. They act as shared analytical frames that help participants articulate needs, clarify constraints, and progressively transform insights into structured service concepts. Their purpose is to provide stable reference points that reduce ambiguity and support communication across diverse stakeholders. Because workshops often bring together actors with different vocabularies, working cultures, and levels of technical familiarity with DestinE, templates serve as artefacts that anchor discussions in concrete representations and facilitate collective understanding.

The templates are designed as a modular set of building blocks, each serving a specific function in the process. Rather than imposing a predefined structure for each workshop, the modularity of the templates allows facilitators to assemble, sequence, or combine them according to the objectives and challenges identified during the co-design diagnosis. A workshop may rely on a single template or on several; another may reuse the same template in a different way, or return to a previous one to refine insights. This flexibility supports an adaptive workshop design, ensuring that the tools remain aligned with the evolving trajectory of the co-design process.

In addition, each template is paired with an exercise that can itself be adapted, shortened, expanded, or reorganized depending on the situation. Exercises can be run in different group settings, integrated into longer sequences or used as stand-alone activities. This second layer of modularity enables facilitators to tailor the intensity, depth, and collective configuration of the discussions without altering the underlying methodological structure. Templates and exercises therefore work together as a flexible kit: the template provides the shared reference frame, while the exercise defines how it is mobilized during the session.

This modular approach also creates coherence across the different phases. A workflow mapping produced early in a Usefulness workshop, for example, can later be revisited during Operability discussions to assess feasibility, and eventually re-examined during Usability sessions to test integration into real practices. In this way, templates support a dynamic and cumulative progression, where insights are deepened step by step rather than reinvented at each session.

Template families and their role throughout the co-design process

The templates are organized into three families that correspond to the core components of the co-design process: **Usefulness**, **Operability**, and **Usability**:

- Usefulness templates (*Worksheet 3.1*) help identify relevant stakeholders, reconstruct workflows, pinpoint pain points, clarify needs, and sketch initial service concepts. They ensure that the co-design process starts from real user situations and avoids premature assumptions or techno-push dynamics.
- Operability templates (*Worksheet 3.2*) shift focus toward feasibility and integration in the platform. They map required data sources and models, describe processing chains, explore integration pathways, and help service providers consider organisational constraints or partnership configurations.
- Usability templates (*Worksheet 3.3*) concentrate on the practical conditions of adoption, examining user journeys, interface expectations, barriers to use, and indicators of successful integration in real contexts.

Although each family contributes differently, they collectively support the progressive convergence from needs, to feasibility, to adoption. This cumulative logic is essential for maintaining coherence across workshops: insights produced early in the process remain visible and actionable in the later phases.

Beyond their role within individual workshops, templates also play a central role in the synthesis phase. Once completed and annotated, they form material that can be used to consolidate findings and fill the outcomes diagram (see *worksheet 4.0*). Because each template captures essential dimensions of user needs, technical conditions, and adoption pathways, they ensure that the final portfolio of actions is grounded, traceable, and directly connected to the workshop discussions.

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